

EBFMC25-OP-26 · Bibliometric Assessment of Global Academic Literature on Commercial Determinants of Health

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Health-damaging commodity industries pose a significant global threat to public health. In particular, the commercial activities of sectors such as tobacco, ultra-processed foods, fossil fuels, and alcohol contribute to the rise in non-communicable diseases, environmental degradation, and health inequalities. The globalization of neoliberal policies has weakened public regulatory mechanisms over commercial actors, resulting in conflicts between public health policies and commercial interests. This study aims to evaluate academic productivity, research trends, and scientific collaborations in the field of Commercial Determinants of Health (CDOH) through a bibliometric methodology.

Materials and Methods: Publications from the years 1961 to 2025 were retrieved from PubMed, Web of Science (WoS), and Scopus databases. Key search terms included "Commercial Determinants of Health," "corporate influence," "industry lobbying," "conflicts of interest," "public health policy," "tobacco industry," and "food industry." Only peer-reviewed journal articles, review studies, and conference proceedings were included. Bibliometric analysis was conducted using the Bibliometrix 4.3.2 package in R.

Results: The number of academic publications in the field of CDOH has increased significantly since 2010, showing a steady upward trend until 2023. Top journals contributing to this field include *Sustainability*, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, and *BMC Public Health*. The most prolific authors identified were Mialon M., Petticrew M., and Maani N. The United States, the United Kingdom, and Australia emerged as the countries with the greatest academic impact. Frequently used keywords included "public health," "corporate social responsibility," "food industry," "tobacco industry," and "marketing."

Conclusion: This study offers a comprehensive analysis of global research trends in the field of CDOH, highlighting the growing academic interest, particularly in the evolution of scientific output and international collaborations. It concludes that future efforts should focus on policy analyses targeting the regulation of sectoral impacts on public health and promoting research in developing countries to address existing knowledge gaps.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

CDOH, food industry, industry lobbying, health inequities, marketing strategies, NCDs, public health policy, tobacco industry, unhealthy commodities

INTRODUCTION

Health-damaging commodity industries pose a significant global threat to public health. In particular, the commercial activities of sectors such as tobacco, ultra-processed foods, fossil fuels, and alcohol contribute to the rise in non-communicable diseases, environmental degradation, and health inequalities. The globalization of neoliberal policies has weakened public regulatory mechanisms over commercial actors, resulting in conflicts between public health policies and commercial interests. These industries are estimated to account for at least one-third of global deaths annually (Gilmore et al., 2023). Their activities not only impact individual health but also contribute to environmental degradation and widening health inequalities. There is increasing scientific evidence that the policies of large multinational corporations exacerbate the prevalence of noncommunicable diseases, environmental harm, and socioeconomic disparities (Lacy-Nichols et al., 2023). In this context, the concept of Commercial Determinants of Health (CDOH) has gained prominence in the academic literature. Notably, the impacts of climate change, the rising burden of non-communicable diseases, and the spread of neoliberal globalization have intensified the adverse effects of commercial sectors on public health. Since the 1970s, the expansion of the neoliberal economic system has progressively weakened public oversight and regulatory policies aimed at mitigating corporate health harms (Friel et al., 2023). As a result, public health policies are increasingly vulnerable to conflicts with commercial interests. In order to enhance the effectiveness of global health strategies, it is critical to strengthen regulatory mechanisms that mitigate the harmful impacts of commercial sectors and to implement comprehensive policy frameworks aligned with the CDOH perspective. This study aims to examine research trends and academic collaborations in the field of CDOH through bibliometric analysis. This bibliometric evaluation provides empirical evidence and serves as a guiding framework for the development of public health policies and regulatory strategies. In analyzing the impact of commercial sectors on public health, this study evaluates the distribution of publications over time, identifies the most influential authors and journals, highlights main research themes, and tracks citation trends. Through this approach, it aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the interaction between commercial sectors and public health policies, and to guide future research in this evolving field.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, a bibliometric analysis was conducted to systematically review scientific research on the Commercial Determinants of Health (CDOH). The literature search was conducted across three major databases: PubMed, Web of Science (WoS), and Scopus. The search strategy included the following keywords and phrases: "Commercial determinants of health," "CDOH," "corporate influence," "industry lobbying," "conflicts of interest," "regulatory capture," "unhealthy commodities," "health inequalities," "health disparities," "public health policy," "noncommunicable diseases," "NCDs," "food industry," "tobacco industry," "alcohol industry," "pharmaceutical industry," "marketing strategies," "corporate social responsibility," "supply chains and health," and "environmental determinants of health." These terms were searched in the title, abstract, and keyword fields. The inclusion criteria comprised peer-reviewed articles, review papers, and conference proceedings published in English or Turkish between 1961 and 2025. Studies published in languages other than English or Turkish were excluded, as well as publications falling outside the defined timeframe or not meeting peer-review standards. The bibliometric analysis was conducted using the R package Bibliometrix (version 4.3.2). The analysis examined trends in the number of publications over time (1961–2025), identified the most frequently cited articles, authors, and journals, and determined the journals and publishing houses with the highest publication output. Additionally, it included network visualization and interpretation of international research collaborations, as well as the identification of prominent thematic areas in the literature. Since this study relied exclusively on publicly accessible bibliometric data, ethics committee approval was not required.

RESULTS

Following the comprehensive literature screening, a total of 3,119 academic documents published between 1961 and 2025 were identified. Specifically, 2,348 records were retrieved from the Web of Science database, 777 from Scopus, and 135 from PubMed. Duplicate records originating from multiple databases were identified and excluded, resulting in 141 duplicates being removed. The analyzed documents involved contributions from 12,611 authors and were published across 783 different academic sources. The international collaboration rate was calculated as 21.99%, while the average number of co-authors per

publication was 4.74. When examining publication trends over time, it was observed that scholarly output remained limited until the early 2000s. However, a marked increase in academic production began after 2010, with an upward trajectory that persisted through 2023. The journals *Sustainability* (151 articles), *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* (142 articles), and *BMC Public Health* ranked among the most prolific in this domain. The most active contributing authors were identified as Mialon M., Petticrew M., and Maani N. In terms of citation impact, the United States (46,710 citations) and the United Kingdom (22,038 citations) led the field, followed by Germany, Australia, and Canada. Frequently recurring keywords in the literature included "public health," "corporate social responsibility," and "tobacco industry." Thematic analysis revealed that during the 1970–1990 period, dominant research topics included chemical exposure and the pharmaceutical industry. Between 1990 and 2010, scholarly attention shifted toward tobacco use, the tobacco industry, and public health policy. After 2010, focus expanded to encompass corporate social responsibility, marketing strategies, and socioeconomic inequalities. Thematic mapping identified "health policies" and "industrial impacts" as motor themes, while "corporate social responsibility" and "sustainability" emerged as niche areas. Education, tobacco consumption, and nutrition also emerged as central thematic areas within the field.

DISCUSSION

This study investigates academic collaborations and evolving patterns of research production on Commercial Determinants of Health (CDOH), with a particular emphasis on how the topic is framed within public health scholarship. Recent years have witnessed a marked increase in academic interest, especially concerning the intersection of commercial factors and public health policy (Friel et al., 2023). This study critically examines the ways in which direct commercial actors acquire structural power through marketing practices and policy influence. Analysis of the most cited authors and journals reveals that CDOH research is predominantly concentrated around specific academic institutions, revealing the formation of a robust yet institutionally concentrated research network. While this demonstrates the emergence of a focused scholarly discourse, it also underscores the need for broader academic participation and more diverse institutional engagement. Cross-national collaboration patterns indicate that research originating from North America, Europe, and Australia dominates the field, whereas scholarly contributions from developing countries remain limited. Expanding research efforts across diverse geographical contexts is essential for a comprehensive understanding of the global health implications of commercial influence. The bibliometric analysis underscores the multifaceted negative impacts of the alcohol and tobacco industries on public health, not only through direct health consequences but also via lobbying and policy interventions (Gilmore et al., 2023). This study explores how commercial actors shape societal norms and influence public policy agendas. Keyword analysis indicates that public health policies, corporate social responsibility, and social inequalities are frequently addressed themes, while issues such as climate change and environmental sustainability remain relatively marginalized within the scholarly discourse. Previous studies have primarily concentrated on identifying and conceptualizing commercial determinants of health (Gilmore et al., 2023; Yildirim & Uyar, 2023). By utilizing bibliometric methods across Web of Science, Scopus, and PubMed, the present study contributes valuable insights into emerging research themes, collaborative structures, and citation dynamics within the CDOH field. While this study offers valuable contributions, certain limitations must be acknowledged. It relies exclusively on publications indexed in three major databases and omits literature published in other languages or across alternative platforms. Furthermore, although bibliometric analysis effectively maps research trends and scholarly influence, it does not provide in-depth qualitative insights. Future studies should adopt multidisciplinary and mixed-method approaches to comprehensively investigate how commercial determinants influence public health outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This study analyzes the development and evolving trends of academic research on Commercial Determinants of Health (CDOH) in the scientific literature. Recent years have witnessed a notable surge in academic interest concerning the effects of commercial factors on public health, with scholarly contributions particularly concentrated in North America, Europe, and Australia. Public health policies, corporate social responsibility, marketing strategies, and industrial impacts have emerged as key themes within the literature. The health effects of the tobacco, food, and alcohol industries are frequently examined in the context of lobbying activities and regulatory policy frameworks (Kalayci Oflaz & Ozen, 2024). Topics such as corporate social

responsibility, socioeconomic inequalities, and public health governance reflect the expanding scope of academic engagement with CDOH. Looking ahead, it will be essential to conduct more robust policy analyses aimed at regulating the influence of commercial industries on public health. Promoting greater research engagement from low- and middle-income countries and fostering interdisciplinary approaches will be critical in addressing persistent knowledge gaps and advancing global strategies to counteract the adverse impacts of commercial determinants of health.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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